

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17737249

Joint Comprehensive Plan Of Action And Iran's Nuclear Programme: A Critical Evaluation

¹Azubiike, Callistus Francis; ²Mbah, Clement Chukwu (Ph.D.) & ³Nwokonye, Agary Ndubuisi (Ph.D.)

Department of Political Science

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria

¹cf.azubiike@unizik.edu.ng +2348035311836

ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-8443-93329>

²mbahclem2@gmail.com

³nwokoye@coou.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study critically evaluated the Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) and its impacts on the Iran's nuclear ambitions. It reviewed the historical background of Iran's nuclear programme and the controversies surrounding it, the negotiations process leading to the 2015 agreement, and the geopolitical complexities surrounding its implementation and challenges. Drawing on the secondary sources, international agency reports, and scholarly analyses, the research applied qualitative methodology and theoretical frameworks rooted in realism and liberal institutionalism to discuss the JCPOA's effectiveness in checkmating Iran's nuclear capabilities. The study throws light on how the agreement achieved short-term success by limiting Iran's uranium enrichment and enabling robust inspections, but later suffered setbacks due to political distrust, regional rivalries, and the unilateral withdrawal of the United States of America in 2018. This development undermined the agreement's sustainability which pushed Iran to resume certain nuclear activities beyond the accord. Recommendations include building broader diplomatic engagements enhancing verification mechanisms, and considering a more comprehensive, inclusive framework often referred to as "JCPOA+" to address regional security concerns. Ultimately, the study contributes to the international discourse on dangers of weapon proliferation, efforts on non-proliferation, global diplomacy and international security with regards to Iran's nuclear activities. In conclusion, the article contributes in bringing to the fore the strengths and weaknesses of JCPOA thereby revealing the limitations of non-binding nature of international agreements in the absence of sustained multilateral commitment.

Keywords: International Security, JCPOA, Nuclear Weapon, Diplomacy, Deterrence

INTRODUCTION

The Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) is a multilateral agreement reached on 14th July 2015 between Iran and the P5+1 group of world powers namely, China, France, the United Kingdom, the United States of America, Germany, and the European Union. The agreement aimed to curb Iran's nuclear activities in exchange for relief from economic sanctions (U.S. Department of State, 2015). Iran's nuclear programme, in turn, refers to the country's development and operation of nuclear technology, officially for peaceful purposes such as energy production, although persistent concerns from the international community, particularly Western powers, have focused on the potential weaponization of this programme (Albright, Heinonen & Stricker, 2015). These global concerns over nuclear threats provided the impetus for the establishment of the Non-Proliferation Treaty (NPT), which seeks to prevent the spread of nuclear weapons while promoting the peaceful use of nuclear

energy. Although Iran is a signatory to the NPT, it has faced repeated accusations of non-compliance (IAEA, 2015). In nuclear terminology, enrichment refers to increasing the proportion of the isotope uranium-235 in uranium, where uranium enriched above 90% is weapon-grade, while 3–5% enrichment is typically used for nuclear power generation (IAEA, 2016). The enforcement of these benchmarks regarding Iran’s nuclear ambitions prompted the negotiation of the JCPOA, alongside sanctions as restrictive measures imposed to influence state behavior and ensure effective control (Katzman, 2017). The JCPOA is globally recognized as a landmark 2015 agreement under which Iran consented to limit and accept monitoring of its nuclear programme in exchange for significant sanctions relief. Negotiated by Iran and the P5+1 countries along with the European Union, the JCPOA aimed not only to curb Iran’s nuclear proliferation risks but also to reintegrate Tehran into the international community (Robinson, 2023). Endorsed by United Nations Security Council Resolution 2231, the agreement represented a major diplomatic breakthrough after more than a decade of tension surrounding Iran’s nuclear ambitions (Mills, 2024).

Despite its initial promise, the JCPOA has remained a polarizing issue in global politics, viewed by some as a model for arms control and by others as an incomplete concession. Iran consistently maintains that its nuclear programme is peaceful and falls within its rights under the NPT, asserting that it has never sought nuclear weapons (Mills, 2024). Western powers, however, have long expressed skepticism, pointing to Iran’s past clandestine activities, particularly undisclosed uranium enrichment facilities revealed in the early 2000s (Hickey, 2022). While the JCPOA initially froze Iran’s enrichment and imposed intrusive inspections by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), critics argue that Iran’s gradual reduction of compliance following the U.S. withdrawal in 2018 has weakened the deal’s effectiveness (Vakil&Bassiri, 2025). By 2023, Iran had enriched uranium to 60% purity and amassed a stockpile far exceeding JCPOA limits, raising fears that its “breakout time”—the period needed to acquire sufficient fissile material for one nuclear weapon had been reduced to mere weeks (Mills, 2024). Supporters of the JCPOA emphasize that until the U.S. withdrawal, Iran was fully compliant, as verified by over a dozen IAEA reports (Robinson, 2023). The deal imposed rigorous restrictions, including limiting uranium enrichment to 3.67%, allowing only a fraction of centrifuges to operate, and providing 24/7 IAEA monitoring at key facilities (Hinderstein, 2025). Strategically, it extended Iran’s breakout time to approximately one year (Mills, 2024). Moreover, the multilateral nature of the agreement, with backing from Russia and China, lent the JCPOA significant international legitimacy (Kaye, 2018).

On the other hand, critics, particularly in the U.S., Saudi Arabia, and Israel, argue that the JCPOA failed to address broader concerns, such as Iran’s ballistic missile programme and regional military interventions (Byman, 2020). They contend that the financial windfall from sanctions relief enabled Iran to strengthen proxy militias and expand its influence in Lebanon, Syria, Yemen, and Gaza (Palestine), while the “sunset clauses,” under which key nuclear restrictions expire after 10–15 years, could allow Iran to resume advanced enrichment with international legitimacy (Kaye, 2018). These critiques influenced President Trump’s decision to withdraw the U.S. from the deal in 2018, citing the JCPOA as fundamentally flawed and strategically inadequate (Scheffer, 2020). The near-collapse of the JCPOA following the U.S. withdrawal has exposed both geopolitical rifts and legal ambiguities in the agreement. Although the U.S. attempted to invoke the deal’s “snapback” mechanism to reintroduce UN sanctions, this move was rejected by other signatories (Scheffer, 2020). European powers, while seeking to preserve the deal, have acknowledged Iran’s partial non-compliance and threatened the reintroduction of sanctions (Mills, 2024). The resulting controversy underscores the fragility of multilateral arms control agreements when unilateral actions undermine collective enforcement.

Given this complex landscape, it becomes imperative to critically assess the JCPOA in terms of both its achievements and limitations. This study, therefore, examined the fundamental objectives that prompted the establishment of the JCPOA and to ascertain the extent to which those objectives have been achieved with respect to Iran’s nuclear programme. In doing so, it evaluated the legal, political, and strategic dimensions of the agreement, highlighting the challenges that have undermined its effectiveness. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions: What were the objectives behind the establishment of the JCPOA? To what extent were these objectives achieved with respect to Iran’s nuclear programme? And what challenges have hindered the realization of these objectives? A balanced and critical evaluation requires weighing the verifiable successes of the

JCPOA, such as stringent monitoring and delayed nuclear advancement, against its strategic omissions and time-limited provisions. While the agreement temporarily constrained Iran’s nuclear programme, it arguably did little to curtail Iran’s broader regional behaviour. At the same time, Western inconsistency and internal divisions weakened enforcement credibility and encouraged gradual Iranian defiance. This research therefore explored the JCPOA from both Western and Iranian perspectives, providing a new understanding of its implications for arms control diplomacy and global nuclear security.

To understand Iran’s nuclear programme and the 2015 Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA), this study adopts a multidisciplinary theoretical lens drawing on realism, constructivism, and liberal institutionalism. Realist theory emphasizes the anarchic international system and state security, framing Iran’s nuclear ambitions as a rational response to regional threats and great power dynamics, with nuclear capability serving as deterrence and strategic autonomy (Waltz, 1981; Mearsheimer, 2001; Waltz, 2012). Constructivist perspectives highlight ideational and identity-based motivations, portraying the programme as a symbol of scientific progress, national pride, and resistance to Western pressure (Adler-Nissen, 2014; Kroenig, 2014). Liberal institutionalism underscores the JCPOA’s reliance on diplomacy, verification mechanisms, and economic incentives to foster stability (Keohane & Nye, 1989; Moravcsik, 1997). Using a qualitative, descriptive approach, this study draws on secondary sources, including UN Security Council Resolution 2231, IAEA reports, government statements, peer-reviewed articles, think-tank analyses, and credible media, employing thematic content analysis to examine verification, sanctions relief, regional implications, and compliance.

Iran’s Uranium Enrichment Trajectory

Source: Simon Henderson and Olli Heinonen (2013) *The Washington Institute for Near East Policy Policy Focus* 121 | May 2013 Update

Using the Diagram in page 3 to explain Iran’s Nuclear Progress

The diagram above illustrated the sequential uranium enrichment process which is a pathway that mirrors Iran’s technical and political pathway from the early stages of its nuclear programme to the present day. Uranium enrichment refers to increasing the concentration of uranium-235 (U-235) isotopes from their natural level of about 0.7% to levels usable in reactors or potentially weapons. Iran’s journey through these stages reveals both scientific progress and shifting international oversight.

1. Initial Stage: 0.7% (Natural Uranium and Early Civilian Program)

Iran’s nuclear programme began in the 1950s under the Shah with U.S. and Western support through the Atoms for Peace initiative. During this period, Iran’s activities centered on natural uranium (~0.7%) for civilian energy and medical research. The Tehran Nuclear Research Center was established in 1967 with a U.S.-supplied 5 MW reactor using uranium enriched to 93%, under

International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) safeguards (Kerr, 2022). After the 1979 Islamic Revolution, cooperation with the West declined, but Iran maintained its ambition for self-sufficiency in nuclear technology, gradually moving toward indigenous uranium conversion and enrichment capabilities (Cordesman & Toukan, 2014)

2. Low Enriched Uranium (LEU): 3.5% – 3.67%

By the early 2000s, Iran began enriching uranium at Natanz to levels around 3.5%, which is typical for civilian power reactors. However, the undeclared nature of these facilities led to international concern and UN Security Council sanctions (Fitzpatrick, 2011). The Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) signed in 2015 limited Iran's enrichment to no more than 3.67% and capped its stockpile at 300 kg of UF₆ for 15 years (U.S. Department of State, 2015). This phase corresponds to the second column in the diagram labeled "3.5%," where enrichment was constrained under strict verification.

3. Intermediate Enrichment: 20% (Research Reactor Level)

By 2010, Iran began to enrich its uranium to 20% apparently to fuel the Tehran Research Reactor, which produces medical isotopes. However, enrichment at this level was seen as a proliferation risk because 20% is technically much closer to weapons-grade than 3.67% (International Atomic Energy Agency [IAEA], 2011). By reaching this level, Iran had demonstrated mastery of critical enrichment technology, symbolized in the diagram's third bar labeled "20%." The 20% threshold marks a pivotal step because going from 20% to 90% requires far fewer separative work units (SWUs) compared to the initial stages (Heinonen & Henderson, 2020).

4. High Enrichment: 60% (Near-Weapons Grade)

Following the U.S. withdrawal from the JCPOA in 2018, Iran progressively breached the agreement's limits. In April 2021, Iran began enriching uranium to 60% at Natanz and Fordow after a sabotage attack on its facilities (Reuters, 2022). At this stage, represented by the "60%" column in the diagram, indicates that Iran had entered a high-enrichment zone rarely associated with peaceful purposes. The IAEA (2023) confirmed that Iran accumulated significant quantities of 60%-enriched uranium, bringing its "breakout time", that is the period needed to produce one bomb's worth of weapons-grade uranium, down to less than two weeks if it chose to proceed (IAEA, 2023; Al Jazeera, 2023).

5. Weapons-Grade Level: 90%

The final stage, 90% enrichment, corresponds to weapons-grade uranium (WGU). Although Iran has not officially enriched to 90%, the IAEA reported in 2023–2024 that Iran had produced uranium particles enriched up to 83.7%, suggesting technical capability near this threshold (Associated Press, 2024). This stage, the "90%" arrow in the diagram, symbolizes the culmination of enrichment capacity that could allow Iran to produce a nuclear weapon if it decided to. Western intelligence and think-tank reports estimate that Iran's technical "breakout" time in 2024–2025 has become extremely short, prompting renewed diplomatic urgency (International Institute for Strategic Studies [IISS], 2024).

Interpretation of the Diagram

The diagram effectively illustrates the non-linear nature of uranium enrichment. Moving from 0.7% → 3.5% → 20% → 60% → 90% is not a simple linear process; most of the effort is expended in the early stages. Once enrichment reaches 20%, the remaining steps require relatively little time and energy. Thus, Iran's progress from 3.67% (JCPOA level) to 60% (post-2021) represents an exponential leap in weapons potential, not just a gradual technical upgrade (Heinonen & Henderson, 2020).

Scholarly Views on the Activities of JCPOA and Iran's Nuclear Pathway

Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA)

The Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA), signed in July 2015 was between Iran and the P5+1 (United States, United Kingdom, France, Russia, China, and Germany), was hailed as a watershed moment in nuclear diplomacy. Portrayed by its architects as a pragmatic and verifiable solution to Iran's contested nuclear programme, the agreement was intended to impose stringent limitations on Iran's nuclear activities in return for relief from crippling international sanctions against Iran (U.S. Department of State, 2015; IAEA, 2016). The establishment of the JCPOA was rooted in long-standing international concerns over Iran's nuclear activities. Although Iran has overtime maintained that its nuclear programme is intended for peaceful purposes, including electricity

generation and medical research (Fitzpatrick, 2011), the secrecy surrounding its enrichment activities raised fears of covert and clandestine weapons development. Since 2002, the combination of International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and Western intelligence agencies uncovered evidence of clandestine uranium enrichment and potential weaponization research (commonslibrary.parliament.uk 2022). These developments, in the context of the broader nuclear non-proliferation regime defined by the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT), necessitated a diplomatic approach that could simultaneously address security concerns and affirm Iran’s rights as a signatory to the NPT.

Below is a table showing the states recognized as nuclear-weapon states (NWS) under the Treaty on the Non Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT) and other states that currently possess nuclear weapons but are not formally NPT-recognized nuclear-weapon states.

S/N	CATEGORY	STATE	NOTES
	NTP Recognized Nuclear-Weapon States (NWS)		
1		United States of America	One of the five states that “manufactured and exploded a nuclear weapon or other nuclear explosive device before 1 January 1967”.
2		Russia	Former Soviet Union successor; included among the five NWS under the NPT definition.
3		United Kingdom	One of the five original NWS under the NPT.
4		France	One of the five original NWS under the NPT.
5		China	One of the five original NWS under the NPT.
	Other States possessing nuclear weapons (not NPT-recognized as NWS)		
1		India	Conducted nuclear tests; not a NPT Recognized
2		Pakistan	Conducted nuclear tests; likewise not an NPT-Recognized NWS.
3		Israel	Widely believed to possess nuclear weapons though has not publicly acknowledged them; not a signatory to NPT as an NWS.
4		North Korea	Once a party to NPT but withdrew; has nuclear-weapons capability.

Sources: (1). The Nuclear Threat Initiative. (2). Arms Control Association

Below is an expanded table of 12 non-nuclear-weapon states (i.e., they are not officially nuclear-weapon states under the Treaty on the Non Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons, or NPT) that are widely considered to have latent or threshold nuclear capability.

S/N	Country	Key indicators of latent/threshold nuclear capability	Notes
1	Japan	Has full fuel-cycle capability (enrichment, reprocessing), large plutonium stockpile, advanced civilian nuclear programme.	Japan is often described as “one screwdriver’s turn from the bomb”.
2	South Korea (Republic of Korea)	Advanced civilian nuclear power, strong industrial/technological base, proximity to nuclear deterrence region	Though less publicly equipped with full fuel-cycle, still assessed high latency.
3	Germany	Advanced technological and industrial base, civilian nuclear infrastructure, allied with nuclear powers	As a NATO member, political constraints exist, but technical capacity is high.
4	Netherlands	Small but advanced nuclear infrastructure, fuel-cycle capabilities (historically) and strong industrial base.	Often listed among “nuclear threshold” states.
5	Canada	Large uranium resources, advanced nuclear technology, civil nuclear power programme.	Has not pursued weaponization, but technical prerequisites are substantial
6	Brazil	Historically had a secret nuclear weapons programme, currently advanced civilian nuclear tech and resources.	Brazil has been described as a “nuclear latent state”.
7	Argentina	Civil nuclear programme, past ambitions, technological base.	Though much less discussed than some others, it appears in academic lists of latent capability.
8	Sweden	Advanced technological base, civil nuclear energy programme, historically considered for nuclear weapons.	Sweden decided against nuclear weapons, but had much of the technical infrastructure.
9	Switzerland	Advanced economy, capable industrial sector, civil nuclear tech; often listed among near-nuclear states.	Political will lacking, but technical potential present.
10	Australia	Large uranium resources, advanced technology, close ally to nuclear powers; included in lists of near-nuclear states.	Australia remains non-nuclear, but the “threshold” potential is often cited
11	Iran	Active nuclear programme, enrichment, stockpiling of fissile-material-related supplies; considered a threshold state.	Although under sanctions and scrutiny, its nuclear capability has raised proliferation concerns.
12	Taiwan (Republic of China)	Advanced industrial and nuclear-technology base, close to high-tech economies; sometimes listed among threshold states.	Political status complicates assessments, but technically it is often included in threshold discussions.

Sources: (1). Wilson Center, Nuclear Latency and Hedging: Concepts, History and Issues. (2014). (2). Albessard, A., Japan’s nuclear latency (IRSEM Étude, 2022). (3). Gupta, A., “Japan and South Korea’s Commitment to Nuclear Latency and Their Nuclear Capabilities” (ICWA, May 2025). (4). Walker, W., On Nuclear Embeddedness and (Ir)Reversibility (Princeton, 2020).

The NPT recognizes only five nuclear-weapon states (NWS) the P5 while obligating all non-nuclear weapon states (NNWS), including Iran, to refrain from developing nuclear arms. However, structural asymmetries in the treaty where NWS are allowed to retain and modernize their arsenals while NNWS are denied the same have continuously generated dissatisfaction among non-nuclear weapon states (Goldblat, 2003; Maerli & Lodgaard, 2003). The JCPOA thus emerged as a confidence-building measure provided the West, by voluntarily accepting limits beyond its NPT obligations, and in the other hands Iran sought to demonstrate goodwill, while the P5+1 attempted to reassure the global

community of non-proliferation integrity. At its core, the JCPOA imposed time-bound restrictions on Iran's nuclear fuel cycle. These included capping uranium enrichment at 3.67% benchmark, limiting the number of operational centrifuges to about 5,060 IR-1 machines, and reducing Iran's uranium stockpile by 98% to 300 kilograms (IAEA. 2015). In addition, the IAEA was granted unprecedented access to nuclear facilities and supply chains under the Additional Protocol and a bespoke procurement channel to monitor dual-use technologies for proper verification and control (Pompeo, M. 2018). These mechanisms extended Iran's nuclear "breakout time" the time needed to produce one bomb's worth of fissile material, from a few months to approximately one year (Krzysztof 2019 p.8-16). Proponents hailed these constraints as a "gold standard" for verification (Nephew, 2016), noting that compliance was consistently affirmed by IAEA reports until the U.S. withdrawal in 2018. Supporters argue that even if the deal was not permanent, its verification architecture delayed proliferation risks and facilitated transparency during its active years (JCPOA 2015).

Despite its achievements, the JCPOA was burdened by structural and geopolitical limitations, first, the agreement contained "sunset clauses" that allowed key restrictions on enrichment and centrifuge development to expire after 10-15 years. Critics warned that this would enable Iran to legally expand its programme in the future, thereby legitimizing a threshold nuclear state (Fitzpatrick. 2016). Secondly, the deal was narrowly focused on the nuclear file but it failed to address Iran's ballistic missile development and regional interventions via proxy groups, which many Western and regional actors, notably Israel and Saudi Arabia, viewed as equally destabilizing (Pompeo, 2018). This selective scope limited the deal's capacity to comprehensively tackle Iran's strategic posture. Thirdly, the JCPOA's legal integrity was undermined by the U.S. unilateral withdrawal in 2018. Despite being a signatory to UN Security Council Resolution 2231, which endorsed the deal, the U.S. re-imposed sanctions under the Trump administration, citing Iran's missile programme and regional activities (Pompeo, 2018). This move fractured the international consensus, emboldened hardliners within Iran, and prompted Tehran to scale back compliance by enriching uranium up to 60% well beyond JCPOA limits. Disagreements over the legal viability of the "snapback" sanctions mechanism further eroded the agreement's enforceability.

The JCPOA's protocol reflects deeper tensions within the non-proliferation regime. The NPT was premised on a normative bargain that NNWS would abstain from nuclear weapons in exchange for peaceful technology and NWS disarmament (Bunn, 2003). Yet, with nuclear disarmament stagnating among NWS and states like India, Pakistan, and Israel operating outside the NPT (Perkovich. 2003), the moral legitimacy of this regime is increasingly questioned. Iran's case thus exemplifies a broader paradox because, while it adhered to the NPT and subjected itself to additional scrutiny through the JCPOA, its status remained that of a sanctioned outlier. Meanwhile, U.S. allies with ambiguous nuclear capabilities, like Israel, have escaped comparable scrutiny. This double standard undermines the credibility of non-proliferation efforts and reinforces Iran's grievances over Western hypocrisy (commons library, 2020).

The Political Economy Behind the JCPOA

The establishment of the JCPOA cannot be understood or evaluated without recognizing the political economy that shaped both Iran's motivations and Western strategic calculations. By 2013, Iran was grappling with severe economic hardship induced by comprehensive U.S., EU, and UN sanctions targeting its oil exports, banking sector, and access to global markets. Inflation soared above 40%, the currency depreciated dramatically, and foreign investment dwindled. This economic strangulation played a pivotal role in bringing Iran to the negotiating table, particularly under the more moderate presidency of Hassan Rouhani (Nephew, 2016). For Western powers, especially the EU and the Obama administration of the U.S.A, the JCPOA also held significant economic and strategic incentives. European corporations lobbied for reengagement with Iran, anticipating access to a large, educated consumer base and lucrative energy contracts.

The JCPOA thus represented a pathway to reintegrate Iran into the global economy while simultaneously reducing the immediate nuclear threat (cfr.org, 2018). Yet, the deal's political economy was inherently without controversies. In the U.S., domestic opposition framed the agreement as appeasement, arguing that the sanctions relief worth tens of billions in unfrozen assets could empower Iran's Revolutionary Guard and fund proxy conflicts in Syria, Iraq, and Yemen etc., (lawfaremedia.org, 2018). These concerns led to the Trump administration's unilateral withdrawal

from the JCPOA in 2018, despite international criticism and Iran's verified compliance. This exit, coupled with a "maximum pressure" sanctions policy, collapsed the economic incentives that underpinned the deal and prompted Iran to resume higher-level enrichment, exacerbating regional tensions (Pompeo, 2018).

Strategic Ambiguity and Regional Implications

Iran's nuclear posture operates within a framework of strategic ambiguity, where its capabilities approach weapons-grade thresholds without openly breaching the NPT. This ambiguity, while denying adversaries the justification for preemptive war, simultaneously deters regional rivals like Israel and Saudi Arabia. Critics argue that the JCPOA, by preserving elements of Iran's nuclear infrastructure, entrenched this posture rather than eliminating it (carnegieendowment.org, 2020). Regionally, the JCPOA sparked divergent reactions, because while Europe embraced the deal as a model for arms control, Israel condemned it as a threat to its security. Arab Gulf states, particularly Saudi Arabia, feared that Iran's post-sanctions economic revival would bolster its regional influence thereby destabilizing the regional security posture. Thus, while the JCPOA aimed to resolve one proliferation crisis, it arguably intensified others by shifting the strategic balance (lawfaremedia.org, 2018). The JCPOA represents both a diplomatic achievement and a cautionary tale, because as some claimed that it has succeeded in delaying Iran's nuclear development and establishing an intrusive verification regime, however, its time-bound restrictions, failure to address broader security concerns, and susceptibility to domestic political shifts rendered it vulnerable. The political economy of the JCPOA marked by sanctions relief, energy interests, and strategic calculations enabled short-term compliance but could not guarantee long-term stability.

CONCLUSION

1. Establishment Rationale of JCPOA

The JCPOA was conceived as a multilateral diplomatic effort to control Iran's nuclear ambitions not to escalate into weaponry, while affirming its rights under the NPT which allows for civil nuclear facilities. It emerged against a backdrop of escalating concerns over Iran's covert nuclear activities, with the intent to delay Iran's breakout time and subject its nuclear infrastructure to international monitoring and verification.

2. Partial Success in Objective Achievement

Before the U.S. withdrawal in 2018 under Trump's administration, the JCPOA have achieved significant verifiable success thus:

1. Iran complied with limitations on uranium enrichment, centrifuge numbers, and uranium stockpiles.
2. The IAEA confirmed consistent Iranian compliance through intrusive inspections.
3. Iran's breakout time was extended from months to over a year.

The Trump administration's unilateral withdrawal however undermined these achievements causing Iran's subsequent scaling back of commitments.

3. Legal and Strategic Ambiguities

The JCPOA agreements contained legal ambiguities, particularly the contested "snapback" mechanism for re-imposing sanctions. Also the Sunset clauses created concerns about Iran's ability to legally expand its nuclear activities after restrictions expire. Again, the deal failed to address Iran's ballistic missile programme and regional interventions, limiting JCPOA's strategic scope. The agreement was experienced skepticism by key regional actors like Israel and Saudi Arabia, who viewed it as emboldening Iran. The U.S. exit weakened international consensus and exposed the weakness in multilateral arms control enforcement. Also Iran's dual role as a signatory to the NPT and a sanctioned state revealed inconsistencies in the global non-proliferation regime.

This study critically evaluated the Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) within the broader context of Iran's nuclear programme, highlighting the complexities of nuclear diplomacy, international trust, and geopolitical interests. It revealed that while the represented a landmark multilateral effort to checkmate Iran's nuclear ambitions diplomacy and verification mechanisms, its implementation faced significant challenges due to political mistrust, unilateral U.S. withdrawal, and regional tensions. The research highlighted that Iran's nuclear ambition is shaped not only by security concerns but, historical grievances and a desire for strategic autonomy. Ultimately, the JCPOA

underscores the fragile nature of international agreements in a polarized global s) emphasizing the need for sustained diplomatic engagement, mutual respect, and r enforcement mechanisms that will guarantee lasting non-proliferation outcomes.

RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER STUDIES

1. Post-JCPOA Scenarios and Alternative

We suggest that future research should look at viable diplomatic alternatives post-JCPOA, such as regional arms control mechanisms or revised multilateral agreements that include missile and proxy interventions.

2. Comparative Study of Non-Proliferation Agreements

A comparative analysis of the JCPOA with other arms control treaties (e.g., North Korea's Agreed Framework or Libya's disarmament) is suggested because it will yield insights into the structural features that determine success or failure.

3. Regional Security Complex and Proxy Dynamics

There is need for an empirical research on how Iran's nuclear posture interacts with her regional influence activities and how this duality shapes Middle East security dynamics, and given the JCPOA's vulnerability to leadership changes (e.g., Barrack Obama to Donald Trump), we suggest that future studies should interrogate how domestic political transitions in signatory states impact the stability and continuity of international agreements.

REFERENCES

- Adler-Nissen, R. (2014). *Opting out of the European Union: Diplomacy, sovereignty European integration*. Cambridge University Press.
- Al Jazeera. (2023, March 1). IAEA confirms Iran enriching uranium up to 60 percent purity. Retrieved from <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2023/3/1/iaea-confirms-iran-enriching-uranium-up-to-60-percent-purity>
- Arms Control Association. (2018). *The Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) at glance*, <https://www.armscontrol.org>
- Arms Control Center. (2018). *Understanding the Iran nuclear deal* <https://www.armscontrolcenter.org>
- Associated Press. (2024, February 27). UN watchdog finds Iran enriched uranium close to weapons grade. Retrieved from <https://apnews.com/article/iran-nuclear-uranium-enrichment-weapons-grade>
- Bunn, G. (2003). The nuclear nonproliferation regime and its history. *Nonproliferation Review* 10(3), 1-19.
- Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. (2020). *Iran's nuclear capabilities after the JCPOA*. <https://carnegieendowment.org>
- Cohen, A. (1998). *Israel and the bomb*. Columbia University Press.
- Cordesman, A. H., & Toukan, A. (2014). *Iran and the Gulf Military Balance*. Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS).
- Council on Foreign Relations. (2018). *What is the Iran nuclear deal?* <https://www.cfr.org>
- Davenport, K. (2018). *The Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA) at a glance*. Arms Control Association, <https://www.armscontrol.org>
- Fitzpatrick, M. (2011). *The Iranian nuclear crisis: Avoiding worst-case outcomes*. Routledge.
- Fitzpatrick, M. (2016). *Assessing the Iran nuclear deal*. International Institute for Strategic Studies.
- Fitzpatrick, M. (2016). *The JCPOA: A flawed but necessary agreement*. *Survival*, 58(1), 55-66.
- Fitzpatrick, M. (2011). *Iran's Nuclear, Chemical and Biological Capabilities: A Net Assessment*. International Institute for Strategic Studies (IISS).
- Goldblat, J. (2003). *Arms control: The new guide to negotiations and agreements*. SAGE Publications.
- Heinonen, O., & Henderson, S. (2020). *Nuclear breakout times: Technical realities and policy dilemmas*. The Washington Institute for Near East Policy.
- International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2015). *Verification and monitoring in the Islamic Republic of Iran in light of United Nations Security Council Resolution 2231 (2015)*. <https://www.iaea.org>

- International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2016). Status report on Iran's nuclear programme, <https://www.iaea.org>
- International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2016). Verification and monitoring in the Islamic Republic of Iran, <https://www.iaea.org>
- International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2011). Implementation of the NPT Safeguards Agreement and relevant provisions of Security Council resolutions in the Islamic Republic of Iran (GOV/2011/65). Vienna: IAEA.
- International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2023). Verification and Monitoring in the Islamic Republic of Iran in light of United Nations Security Council Resolution 2231 (2015). Vienna: IAEA.
- International Institute for Strategic Studies (IISS). (2024). Iran's Nuclear Programme: Technical progress and strategic implications. London: IISS.
- Kaye, D. D. (2020). Reimagining diplomacy: Towards a JCPOA+. RAND Corporation. <https://www.rand.org>
- Keohane, R. O. & Nye, J. S. (1989). Power and interdependence (2nd ed.). Harper Collins.
- Kerr, P. K. (2022). Iran's Nuclear Program: Status. Congressional Research Service (CRS Report RL34544). Washington, DC.
- Kroenig, M. (2014). A time to attack: The looming Iranian nuclear threat. St. Martin's Press Lawfare Media. (2018). The flaws in the Iran nuclear deal, <https://www.lawfaremedia.org>
- Maloney, S. (2015). Iran's political economy since the revolution. Cambridge University Press.
- Mearsheimer, J. J. (2001). The tragedy of great power politics. W. W. Norton.
- Maerli, M. B., & Lodgaard, S. (2003). Nuclear proliferation and international security. In Nuclear proliferation and international security (pp. 1-23). Routledge.
- Moravcsik, A. (1997). Taking preferences seriously: A liberal theory of international politics. *International Organization*, 51(4), 513-553.
- Nephew, R. (2016). The art of sanctions: A view from the field. Columbia University Press.
- Perkovich, G. (2003). India's nuclear bomb: The impact on global proliferation. University of California Press.
- Pompeo, M. (2018, May 21). After the deal: A new Iran strategy. U.S. Department of State. <https://www.state.gov>
- Reuters. (2022, November 22). Iran enriches uranium to 60% purity at Fordow plant: IAEA report. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/world/middle-east/iran-enriches-uranium-60-purity-fordow-plant-2022-11-22/>
- UK House of Commons Library. (2023). Iran's nuclear programme and the JCPOA. <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk>
- U.S. Department of State. (2015). The Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA). <https://2009-2017.state.gov>
- U.S. Department of State. (2015). Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA). Washington, DC: Author. Retrieved from <https://2009-2017.state.gov/e/eb/tfs/spi/iran/jcpoa/index.htm>
- Waltz, K. N. (1981). Theory of international politics. Addison-Wesley.
- Waltz, K. N. (2012). Why Iran should get the bomb. *Foreign Affairs*, 91(4), 2-5.